

Anthropological analysis of human remains from the biritual cemetery at Opole-Groszowice, Poland

A total of 33 burial contexts were subjected to anthropological analysis, including 32 cremation burials and one inhumation grave (Grave 154). The osteological material was generally poorly preserved. Among the cremated remains, there was a marked overrepresentation of shaft fragments of long bones, which is typical for heavily fragmented, heat-altered assemblages. The skeletal remains from the inhumation burial (Grave 154) were preserved only as fragmented portions of the cranial vault.

During the anthropological study, both human and animal bones were weighed. Each sample was assessed for the degree of burning, coloration, and crack patterns; the minimum number of individuals (MNI) was estimated, along with biological sex and age at death (Dokládál, 1999; Gładkowska-Rzeczycka, 1977; Hunger & Rother, 1978; Strzałko et al., 1973; Ubelaker, 1978). Additionally, basic paleodemographic parameters were calculated (Budnik & Pudło, 2022; Piontek, 1985). When possible, estimations of living stature were conducted, and observed skeletal pathologies were documented (Strzałko et al., 1972).

The total weight of human cremated remains ranged from 2.68 to 1685.14 grams ($\bar{X} = 219.14$ g; SD = 404.46; Me = 27.39 g) (Fig. S1). The remains were predominantly categorized as heavily and fully calcined (burning grades 4 and 4/5), exhibiting white, light yellow, or light gray coloration (Dokládál, 1999). Most of the assemblages showed uniform exposure to high temperatures and were assigned a single burning stage. However, in Graves 121 and 146, differential burning was recorded. Transverse, reticulated, and curved cracks were noted across many of the bones.

In total, 37 individuals were identified across the 33 burial contexts. Most graves (87.9%) contained the remains of single individuals. However, four double burials were identified (Graves 113, 115, 117, and 130). In three of these (113, 117, 130), adult individuals of indeterminate sex were found together with children (Infans I). In Grave 115, the remains of an adult female (or probably female) and another adult of undetermined sex were distinguished.

Biological sex could be determined for nine individuals (24.3%) – seven were identified as female and two as male. Additionally, ten petrous parts of temporal bone (pars petrosa ossis temporalis, PP) from eight graves (110, 113, 129, 136, 138, 140, 141, 144) were analyzed using the lateral angle method (LA) (Fig. S2). The sex estimation was based on a threshold value of 45° ($K \geq 45^\circ < M$) (Afacan et al., 2017; Graw et al., 2005; Hałuszko & Guziński, 2022; Norén et al., 2005; Waltenberger et al., 2024). This method identified five females and three males. The average angle for females was 53.4° , and for males, 38.9° . An osteometric method using postcranial skeletal elements was applied to remains from five individuals (Graves 110, 115, 120, 130, and 141), all of whom were classified as female.

Postcranial measurements were also used to reconstruct living stature. For four females (Graves 110, 115, 120, and 141), estimated body height ranged from short to medium categories.

Fig. S1. Opole-Groszowice, site 110 (AZP 90-37/41). Mass of cremated human bones: A – histogram with 100-gram intervals and fitted density curve; B – preserved cranial fragments, including roots of permanent teeth and shafts of long bones from the individual in Grave 120; C – distribution, and D – cumulative distribution of bone mass by skeletal element categories. Prepared by A. Hałaszkó.

Age at death was estimated for 30 individuals (81.1%). Of these, 20 individuals (54.1%) were assigned to specific age categories, while 10 (27.0%) were classified generally as “adult.” The highest number of individuals died in the Adultus category (10 individuals), followed by Infans I (4 individuals). Three individuals were categorized as Maturus, and one each as Infans I/II and Juvenis/Adultus. Age at death could not be determined for seven individuals.

Based on life tables constructed from the demographic data, the crude life expectancy at birth (e_0) was estimated at approximately 22 years (Table S1). After correcting for underrepresented subadult mortality (ages 0–14.9, d_0 –14.9), the adjusted life expectancy at birth ranged between 12.2 and 13.5 years. Adults (e_{20}) had an average life expectancy exceeding 27 years. These

estimates correspond with a high index of natural selection among adults ($I_f = 44.6\%$). The potential reproductive rate ($R_{pot} = 78.9\%$) was high, as was the proportion of child mortality. The index of biological state ($I_{bs} = 36.7\%$) was low. The population structure, reflected in the C_x parameter, suggests a stable demographic profile. Mortality rates (m_x) were standard, and no evidence was found for improved biological condition due to socioeconomic factors.

Fig. S2. Opole-Groszowice, site 110 (AZP 90-37/41). Preserved fragments of the petrous part of the temporal bone (*pars petrosa ossis temporalis*). Photo by A. Hałuszko.

Among the skeletal assemblages from the Opole-Groszowice cemetery, four individuals (Graves 113, 115, 125, and 141) exhibited hypertrophic bone changes (Fig. S3). These included *cribra orbitalia* (porous lesions in the orbital roof) and *hyperostosis parietalis* (porous expansion of the parietal bones and occipital squama).

Stable isotope analysis of carbon ($\delta^{13}\text{C}$) and nitrogen ($\delta^{15}\text{N}$) was performed on collagen extracted from an adult female or probable female aged 40–50 years, interred in Grave 154 (inhumation burial). The measured isotope values ($\delta^{13}\text{C} = -17.92\text{‰}$; $\delta^{15}\text{N} = 10.18\text{‰}$) suggest a diet characterized by a relatively high intake of animal protein, potentially including terrestrial meat, freshwater fish, and/or dairy products. The elevated $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ value may indicate some contribution of C_4 plants (such as millet) or animals that consumed C_4 plants, which is notable given the predominance of C_3 plants in temperate Europe. This pattern aligns with dietary flexibility or specific cultural food practices during the period under study.

However, the collagen sample exhibited an atomic carbon-to-nitrogen (C/N) ratio of 3.8, which exceeds the widely accepted quality control range for well-preserved archaeological collagen

(2.9-3.6). Such a value implies potential diagenetic alteration or contamination, possibly from soil-derived organic matter, conservation treatments, or degradation processes affecting collagen integrity. This contamination raises concerns about the accuracy of the isotope measurements, as extraneous carbon or nitrogen sources can skew the $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ signatures.

Given these limitations, the isotopic data must be interpreted with caution. While the values provide a useful preliminary indication of diet, further analyses – such as additional sampling from the same individual or other contemporaneous individuals, and complementary biomolecular methods – are recommended to validate these findings. Understanding the dietary habits through stable isotopes remains crucial for reconstructing subsistence strategies and cultural practices at the Opole-Groszowice site, but the current data highlight the challenges posed by collagen preservation in cremation or mixed burial contexts.

Fig. S3. Opole-Groszowice, site 110 (AZP 90-37/41). Pathological bone changes observed as hyperostosis porotica in individuals from Graves 113 (A1, A2, A3), 115 (B1, B2), and 125 (C1, C2, C3), and cribra orbitalia identified in individuals from Graves 115 (B3) and 141 (D1, D2, D3). Photo by A. Hałuszko.

Table S1. Opole-Groszowice, site 110 (AZP 90-37/41). Life table based on data from individuals recovered from skeletal burials: for N = 37.0 before extrapolation, N = 71.8 after estimating missing individuals with $Uc = 6$ (57.8%), and N = 83.5 with $Uc = 7$ (63.8%).

Age group	<i>Dx</i>	<i>dx</i>	<i>lx</i>	<i>qx</i>	<i>Lx</i>	<i>Tx</i>	<i>ex</i>	<i>Dx</i>	<i>dx</i>	<i>lx</i>	<i>qx</i>	<i>Lx</i>	<i>Tx</i>	<i>ex</i>	<i>Dx</i>	<i>dx</i>	<i>lx</i>	<i>qx</i>	<i>Lx</i>	<i>Tx</i>	<i>ex</i>
0-6,9 years	6,3	16,9	100,0	0,2	640,9	2220,0	22,2	37,2	52,0	100,0	0,5	518,1	1351,7	13,5	48,0	57,4	100,0	0,6	499,1	1218,6	12,2
7-14,9 years	0,5	1,4	83,1	0,0	577,0	1579,1	19,0	4,1	5,8	48,0	0,1	315,9	833,7	17,4	5,3	6,4	42,6	0,1	275,8	719,6	16,9
15-19,9 years	1,0	2,7	81,8	0,0	402,0	1002,1	12,3	1,0	1,4	42,2	0,0	207,7	517,7	12,3	1,0	1,2	36,2	0,0	178,0	443,8	12,3
20-29,9 years	22,2	60,0	79,0	0,8	490,5	600,1	7,6	22,2	31,0	40,8	0,8	253,4	310,1	7,6	22,2	26,6	35,0	0,8	217,2	265,8	7,6
30-39,9 years	6,5	17,7	19,1	0,9	102,5	109,6	5,7	6,5	9,1	9,9	0,9	52,9	56,6	5,7	6,5	7,8	8,4	0,9	45,4	48,5	5,7
40-49,9 years	0,5	1,4	1,4	1,0	7,1	7,1	5,0	0,5	0,7	0,7	1,0	3,7	3,7	5,0	0,5	0,6	0,6	1,0	3,1	3,1	5,0
50-x years	0,0	0,0	0,0		0,0	0,0		0,0	0,0	0,0		0,0	0,0		0,0	0,0	0,0		0,0	0,0	
Total	37,0	$d_{0-14,9}=18,2\%$						71,8	$d_{0-14,9}=57,8\%$						83,5	$d_{0-14,9}=63,8\%$					

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